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NEW PRODUCTION TERMINALS – A REFLECTION OF A DEVELOPING ERA IN UZBEKISTAN

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***Abstract.** In world linguistics, terms have attracted the attention of linguists as an internal mechanism that demonstrates the unique capabilities of each language and, undoubtedly, serves to enrich its vocabulary. Terminology is an important factor in the development of a language. In this direction, especially in the film industry, the study of the issue of production terminology, which is considered a productive link, helps to clarify issues such as the relationship between production and terminology, the contribution of terminology to language development, and the level of language development. In particular, the production terms of a particular country are an important source for studying the changes that have occurred in the lexical-semantic and grammatical structure of the formation of the national language at the stages of the language development of this people.*

***Keywords.** term, terminology, production, New Uzbekistan.*

Introduction. In recent years, effective work has been carried out in Uzbek linguistics in the field of terminology that defines and explains the relationship between language and national culture. "Each nation, every independent state should give priority to the preservation and development of its culture, age-old values, and mother tongue in order to ensure its national interests"¹. In the process of reforms being carried out in our country, in addition to improving the living standards of our people, a number of works are being carried out to study our rich national values, customs and traditions,

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 26 майдаги “Маданият ва санъат соҳасининг жамият ҳаётидаги ўрни ва таъсирини ошириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПФ-6000-сон Фармони.

conduct scientific and practical research, preserve our tangible and intangible cultural heritage, convey it to future generations in its entirety, and, of course, widely promote it among the peoples of the world. In order to develop the sphere of culture and art, our esteemed head of state has adopted important decrees and decisions at the level of state policy, and the necessary documents are being directed for implementation. If development in any society is not based on cultural and national values, or if the people and nation have not sufficiently achieved an understanding of who they are, such development will not yield the expected results, whether in the economic or social spheres. Preserving our culture, national values and national spirituality, and achieving their harmony with universal and national values is one of the main goals. The Decree of the Head of State dated May 26, 2020 “On measures to increase the role and influence of the sphere of culture and art in the life of society” will undoubtedly create very broad opportunities for us to achieve such a noble goal as the use of our national values as an integral part of world development.

Literature analysis. Issues such as terminology and its theoretical foundations in world linguistics, the formation and systematization of linguistic terms and their meaning have been specially studied in the research of such scientists as G.O. Vinokur, V.V. Vinogradov, A.A. Reformatsky, O.S. Akhmanova, A.M. Shcherbak, V.P. Danilenko, A.N. Kononov, E.A. Kolesnikova, V.M. Boguslavsky. Terminology can be recognized as a rapidly developing area in Uzbek linguistics. After the 1960s, the study of various terminological systems of the Uzbek language became popular. In the process of reforms being carried out in our country, in addition to improving the living standards of our people, a number of works are being carried out to study our rich national values, customs and traditions, conduct scientific and practical research, preserve our tangible and intangible cultural heritage, convey it to future generations in its entirety, and, of course, widely promote it among the peoples of the world. In order to develop the sphere of culture and art, our esteemed head of state has adopted important decrees and decisions at the level of state policy, and the necessary documents are being directed for implementation. If development in any society is not

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Analysis and results. The 21st century is described as the century of information, communication and creative industries. In this era, production activity has become the main link in the creation of not only art, but also media, advertising, cinema, music,

¹Джамалханов Х. Из истории формирования и развития узбекской ботанической терминологии: автореф. дисс... канд.филол.наук. – Ташкент, 1966; Дониёров Р. Ўзбек тили техник терминологиясининг айрим масалалари. – Тошкент, 1977; Базарова Д.Х. История формирования и развитие зоологической терминологии узбекского языка. – Ташкент, 1978; Касымов А.И. Фармацевтическая терминология в современном узбекском языке: автореф. дисс... канд.филол.наук. – Ташкент, 1982; Мадвалиев А. Узбекская химическая терминология и вопросы её нормализации: автореф. дисс... канд.филол.наук. – Ташкент, 1986; Дадабаев Х. Общественно-политическая и социально-экономическая терминология в тюркоязычных письменных памятниках XI–XIV вв. – Ташкент, 1991; Мирахмедова З. Ҳозирги ўзбек тилининг анатомик терминологияси: филол.фан.номз...дисс. – Тошкент, 1994; Абдуллаева Ч.С. Русско-узбекские параллели в современной экономической терминологии: дисс... канд.филол.наук. – Ташкент, 2000; Йўлдошев И. Ўзбек китобатчилиги терминологияси: шаклланиши, тараққиёти ва тартибга солиш: филол.фан.док...дисс. – Тошкент, 2005; Адиханов Д. Формирование экономической терминологии в современном арабском литературном языке: дисс...канд.филол.наук. – Ташкент, 2010; Аҳмедов О.С. Солиқ ва божхона терминларини инглиз тилидан ўзбек тилига берилиши: филол.фан.номз...дисс.автореф. – Тошкент, 2011; Джурабаева З.А. Ўзбек тилида экологик терминлар: филол.фан.бўйича фласафа док. (PhD) ... дисс.автореф. – Тошкент, 2018.

theater and Internet content. In this process, new terms, namely production terminals, are emerging in the language system. They reflect the socio-economic and cultural reality of the developing era¹. First of all, what is the essence of production activities in this era? As is known, the word “producer” comes from the English term producer and means “developer”, “project organizer”, “leader of the creative process”. In Uzbekistan, the term “producer” began to be used since the middle of the 20th century. Until then, it was mostly directors, composers, singers, choreographers and those involved in other fields (for example, from sports performances to various folk games or wrestlers, doormen) who demonstrated their art in various forms and conditions. They tried to implement all creative and organizational processes, taking responsibility for themselves². In modern culture, it acts as a bridge between art and economics. Therefore, the vocabulary related to the field of “production” is rapidly expanding. Formation of new terms. In recent years, the following production terms have been actively used in the language, which are used in new or new meanings:

Showrunner - the executive producer and creative director of the series;

Creative producer - the creative person responsible for determining the ideological direction of the project;

Music clearance - the process of determining the rights to the music used in the film, and then negotiating permission for this music. All legal actions must be taken before using any piece of music. Otherwise, you may face lawsuits and complaints and pay large fines for copyright infringement.

Line producer - a producer responsible for technical and organizational issues;

Media manager, content producer, social media producer - specialists involved in the creation and distribution of content in the digital space;

Words such as *brand producer*, event producer, sound producer, etc., represent specific industry directions. These terms are often directly borrowed from English or used in a hybrid form, for example, as “creative producer”, “event organizer”;

¹ Гацук-Шерпилова В. Ю. Исторические аспекты развития продюсирования в России // Научно-методический электронный журнал «Концепт». – 2016. – с. 3

² Sayfullayev B., Rustamov V. Prodyuserlik mahorati asoslari. – T.: «Fan va texnologiya», 2015 – B. 9.

Musical explication is a list of musical works, main themes, musical background themes, songs and musical noises, conceived and created by the composer at the request of the director to implement the artistic idea of the upcoming film. Usually, the director imagines a musical solution before shooting the film. The director discusses his musical composition with the film composer before shooting and later formulates it on paper in the form of a musical explication on paper.

The emergence of new terms under the influence of global communication and the digital economy is a natural process. Today, the production industry is taking on a transnational form through the Internet, streaming platforms and social networks. At the same time, the local language system is adapting these terms based on its own rules, adding national meaning to them. For example, such variants as “project manager”, “creative organizer”, “information producer” have also emerged. New production terms are not only lexical innovations, but also a living indicator of language development. Morphological changes are also observed in them (for example, “production”, “without production”, “related to production”). This demonstrates the ability of the Uzbek language to accept global terms and adapt them to the national system.

Conclusion. New production terms are a direct reflection of the developing era. They reflect the dynamics of the modern creative industry, technological innovations and cultural integration processes. From a linguistic point of view, the study of these terms is of great importance not only for lexicology, but also for sociolinguistics and cultural linguistics.

Literature.

1. Винокур Г.О. О некоторых явлениях словообразования в русской технической терминологии. – Москва: Наука, 1939. – 236 с.
2. Гацук-Шерпилова В. Ю. Исторические аспекты развития продюсирования в России // Научно-методический электронный журнал «Концепт». – 2016. – № S14. – 0,3 п. л.
3. Зиямухамедова Ш. Ўзбек тилшунослигида замонавий ахбороткоммуникация терминларининг ўрганилиши. "Oriental Art and Culture" Scientific-Methodical Journal - (3) III, 2020 – 500-510 б.
4. Реформатский А.А. Что такое термин и терминология // Вопросы терминологии // Материалы всесоюзного терминологического совещания. – Москва: АН СССР, 1961. – С.87.
5. Роднянский А. Выходит продюсер. – М.: «Манн, Иванов и Фербер», 2013.
6. Sayfullayev B., Rustamov V. Prodyuserlik mahorati asoslari. – T.: “Fan va texnologiya”, 2015 – 256 b.
7. Толикина Е.Н. Некоторые лингвистические проблемы изучения термина // Лингвистические проблемы научно-технической терминологии. – Москва: Наука, 1970. – 107 с.